

Intra-School Professional Development Training Model In Ict Integration In Teaching: Reflections Of A Teacher

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Abstract

Background: Many teachers still need the appropriate knowledge, skills and training to ensure effective ICT integration in their subjects. The group training that is sometimes provided by district office personnel, National Department of Education or Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO) for efficient use of training leaves many behind as they attend. They are primarily at different competency levels regarding ICT skills, access, and local(internal) or limited external support. Aim: In this regard, the research aimed to investigate the effective use of the Intra-School Professional Development (ISPD) approach to facilitate ICT training to teach Natural Sciences subject in a South African public school. Materials and Methods: The study employed a participatory action research approach focusing on qualitative descriptive case study research. A sample of a grade 6 Natural Science teacher who teaches in an Ex-model C school in the Johannesburg South was selected for the study. The class size ranges between 30-35 learners in a class. The study utilised a semi-structured interview, observation notes, and reflection journal of training as instruments. The semi-structured interview contained open-ended questions and was designed to investigate the factors causing the low utilisation of ICT in the teaching of Natural Science. Results: The findings from the research showed that implementing the ISPD model can maximise the integration of ICT in teaching Natural Science with immediate support from the participant level without waiting or delaying others. The single participant could determine the pace of her growth to independent exploration of the ICT tools in the teaching and learning classroom preparation and practice. Recommendations: The study recommends that in addition to the ICT hardware already provided, the South African Department of Education should also provide subject-specific and grade-appropriate ICT training that provides consistent and immediate support for teachers to integrate effectively.

Introduction

Since the introduction of twenty-first-century learning, there has been a rising demand for technology usage in all aspects of life. Information and Communication Technologies have become increasingly prominent in all fields, including education. Research studies have shown that Integrating Information and Communication Technologies in teaching and learning positively impacts learners' learning outcomes (Mhlanga & Mloi, 2020). Despite the difficult teaching and learning conditions in South Africa, ICT and its role in education cannot be ignored in South Africa (Blignaut, 2006). The rapid development of ICT internationally has stimulated debate about these technologies' role in improving education and accelerating social development in a developing country such as South Africa. Through the e-Education White Paper, the South African government has strongly committed to using ICT in education (Department of Education (DoE), 2004). The White Paper sets out the government's response to a new international information and communication environment in education, focusing on developing studies twenty-first-century skills (Department of Education (DoE), 2004). Implementing these comprehensive strategic policy goals requires a multi-year implementation strategy with three phases, the third and last being that ICT should be integrated at all levels of the education system (2010–2013). Despite this, teachers are still challenged with integrating technology into their teaching due to the lack of training in ICT integration, competencies and knowledge for many of them even when resources have been provided.

Background

From 2019 to 2021, the world was affected by a global pandemic that left the entire world restricted, countries and their people isolated and confined to their homes. Regulations were implemented to restrict physical contact

and formal and social gatherings. This hugely affected the normal functioning of various businesses, universities and schools (Mhlanga & Moloi, 2020). This meant schools had to close for an unknown period for the education sector, disrupting everyday face-to-face teaching. This dramatically changed the education system in South Africa (Mhlanga & Moloi, 2020). In the broader context of Africa and specifically South Africa, the necessity to salvage the academic year prompted a significant shift toward remote and online learning. Responding to this need, the South African government collaborated with numerous non-governmental entities to formulate strategies for continuous education delivery. Various initiatives emerged, utilising online, mobile, and social media platforms such as the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) Lockdown Digital School, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and WhatsApp groups. The government partnered with diverse mobile network providers to facilitate "zero-rated" educational applications. Despite these efforts, many South African government schools faced challenges due to inadequate preparation (Dube, 2020). The lack of prior experience with major epidemics in recent years left the country, specifically the education system, with limited emergency response measures. The diverse contexts of learners also significantly complicate South Africa's endeavours to deliver education effectively during the COVID-19 pandemic.

ICT became part of everyday life post the pandemic for teaching and learning. Before the pandemic, it had seemed that integrating ICT was optional for many teachers, but that quickly changed. Despite the DoE making provisions to enhance teaching and learning through the establishment of computer laboratories with the internet in most schools, the construction of local media centres and classrooms with whiteboards in many urban schools, and the provision of tablets and laptops to teachers and learners (DoE, 2020), it appears the DoE system saw a disparity between teachers' implementation of ICT in pedagogical practices and the education department's expectations.

While the education system developed "in-service training policies and programs to enable teachers to understand and use ICTs appropriately" (DoE, 2004, p. 25), there is still a challenge with implementing ICT policies and ICT programs in some schools. According to the Strategic Plan 2011-2014 of the Department of Basic Education (DBE), capacity was created to support the implementation of the e-Education White Paper. Among the strategic objectives outlined in the White Paper on e-Education (DoE, 2004) is ICT professional development for management, teaching and learning. However, the DoE's efforts in planning and providing resources to schools to integrate ICT in teaching and learning were still insufficient to effectively provide teachers with the necessary training and development to encourage them to use ICT in their teaching practice. The biggest issue that impedes the use and integration of ICT by teachers is the limitation of ICT professional development (Dlamini & Mbatha, 2018). *"If teachers are not informed and trained adequately in using ICT, they will not have the confidence to use ICT in their practice"* Dlamini and Mbatha (2018).

In schools where ICT resources are available for teachers and learners, schools still need more professional development activities to develop digital fluency and adopt and integrate technology in the classrooms (Dlamini & Mbatha, 2018). Both in-service and pre-service teachers face the reality of emerging ICT tools and devices and the daunting task of integrating them into their classrooms. More effective professional development activities and programs are needed to improve ICT integration. Several factors that affect ICT integration, such as personal characteristics, educational level, age, gender, educational experience, and attitude towards computers, can influence the adoption of ICT (Dube, Nhamo&Magonde, 2018). The mere presence of computers in a school does not guarantee the use of ICT tools. Teachers' attitudes towards ICT are believed to strongly indicate whether they will use ICTs (Dube, Nhamo&Magonde, 2018). The teachers with a higher chance of integrating ICTs successfully have more experience, confidence and a positive attitude in their ability to use them effectively.

Additionally, a research study conducted by Dube, Nhamo and Magonde (2018) indicates a need for pedagogical training within teachers' programs, hindering their effective integration of ICTs in the classroom. The study also highlights that while individual ICT skills for personal use may be proficient, the challenge lies in transferring these skills to the educational setting. Providing pedagogical training in ICT integration across the curriculum is an increasingly relevant topic (Mathipa&Mukhari, 2014). While the DoE may have planned and provided resources, it still rests on the schools, principals and school management to ensure that teachers are developed. Efforts should be focused on training, exposing, and motivating teachers to use ICT in their teaching. The more teachers learn, train, and use ICT beyond personal level use, the more teachers will be encouraged to incorporate ICT in their teaching and learning.

Statement of the Problem

There is a growing consensus in literature that ICT professional developments provide teachers with basic computer skills, yet they are expected to integrate ICT effectively into their teaching and learning. UNESCO (2018) maintains that teachers need training in computer literacy and the pedagogical application of those skills

to teaching and learning. Many urban schools and ex-model C schools, such as the one selected for this study, have the appropriate ICT equipment for teachers and learners. All teachers and learners have access to laptops, smartboards and the Internet. However, teachers only use these tools for personal and administrative use rather than in their teaching. Even when teachers use these technologies, it's usually limited to displaying images or playing videos, which happens only occasionally. Despite the availability of resources like smartboards, laptops for each student, and internet access in the selected school for the study, these ICT tools could be more effectively utilised in teaching and learning due to a lack of teacher confidence, appropriate ICT skills, and support.

The researcher's observation, which is not supported by scientific evidence (observational evidence), revealed that there is low utilisation of ICTs in the school of choice in curriculum delivery. Natural Science lessons take place only in the classroom using traditional teaching materials and tools such as pen and paper, textbooks and workbooks. While the use of ICTs seems to be prevalent in lesson planning and recording of marks, the use of ICTs in the actual practical and theoretical lesson delivery remained subdued. All Natural Science lessons follow the same redundant format with little use of ICTs. The primary aim of this study was to develop an innovative and effective training program known as the Intra-School Professional Development model. This program aimed to enhance teachers' abilities to integrate ICT into their teaching practices successfully and examine their experiences in navigating obstacles, changes in attitude and professional growth during this training. Intra-School Professional Development takes a peer-to-peer training approach to provide continuous ICT support.

The main research objective was to investigate:

- How can implementing an Intra-School Professional Development approach facilitate the integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in teaching?

Literature Review

The role of curriculum development in economic development

The ideal curriculum should blend industry and employer expectations, along with the learning interests of learners. However, this integrated approach has yet to be widely implemented. Our rapidly changing world, characterised by ever-evolving knowledge and technologies, our educational systems must adapt to shifting economic trends and goals. Society is investing more time, money and resources in education than ever (Dowelani&Dowelani, 2020). South Africa aims to harness the potential of technological innovation to grow its economy and uplift the people by 2030 (Enaifoghe, Balogun, & Afolabi, 2021). Individual educational attainment is now crucial for future success in personal and societal contexts (Geo-Jaja &Zajda, 2005; Soudien, 2007; Cheng, Lu, Xie, &Vongkulluksn, 2020). Education is the primary vehicle for human and social development. Adler and Isaacs (1983) highlighted three core purposes of education: citizenship development, personal growth/self-improvement, and occupational preparation. To fulfil these objectives, education must be tailored to meet the specific needs of local and national communities (Geo-Jaja &Zajda, 2005). Thus, the emergence of a global economic and social order necessitates new educational policies and strategies informed by market research and tailored to market needs. Scholars are underlining the role of the education system in shaping future technology by becoming the testbed for innovation and teaching future generations (Cloete, 2017). Critics contend that a mismatch exists between twentieth-century teaching methodologies and the needs of twenty-first-century learners, who are deeply influenced by the digital revolution.

The ICT policy in education

The integration of ICT into teaching is influenced by various critical factors, as evident from a comprehensive literature review. Governments often emphasise providing hardware and infrastructure in their ICT in education policies. Still, they need to adequately address how ICT should be practically used in classrooms and schools. Clearer policy guidelines are often needed to support schools, which can hinder the effective implementation of ICT policies. The introduction of ICT into schools requires revisions to the national curriculum. However, there is often a need for a shared vision among relevant stakeholders regarding what effective ICT integration in teaching and learning truly means. The gap between policy requirements and actual classroom practice can be found to be substantial (Underwood et al., 2007). Within the South African context, research in ICT is described as "under-theorised." There is a notable lack of research regarding relevant ICT policies and their impact on schools. While South Africa has established comprehensive policy frameworks for ICT, implementing these policies in classrooms remains challenging (Blignaut& Howie, 2009). The integration of ICT into the curriculum and the development of effective management strategies for its implementation across all schools are ongoing processes. Additionally, Institutional culture and leadership at the school level are vital for successfully implementing government ICT policies (Ng & Ho, 2012). These factors can significantly influence how ICT is integrated into teaching and learning practices.

Understanding the integration of ICT

The effectiveness of integrating ICT in the classroom is critical and needs highlighting (Ghavifekr&Rosdy, 2015; Hero, 2020; Maru, Pikirang, Ratu & Tuna, 2021; Shah, 2022). The current use of technology in schools often needs more creativity and leveraging digital tools for meaningful, in-depth learning experiences. Many teachers still approach technology as a means of content delivery rather than a tool for fostering creativity, collaboration and critical thinking. Not only are the technologies themselves premised on traditional pedagogies, but the ways teachers have been using technology with learners are also more about delivery than creativity. The current use of technology inside schools and classrooms rarely leverages digital tools and resources for deep learning. The data from Fullan (1993) and Fullan and Langworthy (2014) indicate that technology in education was primarily used in basic ways, where it was added as a layer on top of traditional teaching and learning methods rather than effectively used for collaboration and knowledge creation. The DBE estimates that a mere 26% of South African teachers are equipped with basic technology skills, with only 7% functioning at an intermediate level of competency (Graham, Stols, & Kapp, 2020). This suggests a need for deeper forms of knowledge creation that align with evolving pedagogies.

Theoretical framework - Intra-School Professional Development

Teacher professional development involves activities or programs designed to enhance teachers' performance in the classroom, ultimately benefiting learners' academic achievements in the education system. Ajani and Govender(2023) suggest that teachers can participate in different aspects of ICT-related professional development programs. These activities may encompass a variety of programs or approaches. This study is built upon the Intra-School Professional Development approach, a powerful approach to boosting teachers' professional growth. ISPD involves a collaborative effort between teachers and the school management team (SMT) to jointly craft programme/s that best use the existing staff to address the school's and its teachers' unique needs (Good & Brophy, 1994).

This model empowers teachers together with the school management team (SMT) to actively plan their professional development program, ensuring that the training is tailored to their school's specific context and teacher's specific needs. Within the ISPD framework, teachers' talents are recognised and used, especially in technical areas like ICT training. This approach lets teachers use their problem-solving abilities to address real challenges, transforming the school into a dynamic learning hub (Handal et al., 2003). Teachers plan their professional development to be personalised to their needs and delivered within the school's unique context. These professional development activities strategically align instructional practices with the school's curriculum. This includes personalised peer-to-peer practical training sessions covering curriculum mapping, lesson planning, and instructional strategies that closely resonate with the educational objectives. Grouping teachers based on their expertise and facilitating mutual learning enhances this collaborative environment. Research has shown that teachers who engage in externally-based training or development often face hurdles when returning to school settings (Burns, 2023). Ultimately, ISPD may be more effective in driving educational changes than traditional training approaches such as once-off workshops. Hennessy and Davies (2019) and Cothorn (2020) found that most teachers from elementary schools reported effective learning from other teachers, while less than half reported successful learning from workshops and conferences.

Intra-school professional development, according to Good and Brophy (1994), can follow the following cycle: professional discussion, curriculum development, peer observation, peer coaching, action research, and university-school system alliances. The study mainly focused on professional discussion, curriculum development, peer observation, and peer coaching. Professional discussion enables teachers to reflect on general professional issues that are of interest and common to them (Leikin and Winicki-Landman, 2001). Professional discussions can take the form of interviews and questionnaires. These issues need not necessarily be related to the specific school context. Still, they may have a broader scope, such as philosophies of education, teachers' beliefs, computer education, problem-solving, parental involvement, investigational work, etc. Teachers may also work cooperatively in curriculum development tasks, developing and sharing knowledge and experiences in designing instructional activities that reflect school needs. In peer observation, teachers collaborate to visit one another's classrooms to identify situations that may assist them in improving teaching. Novice teachers, in particular, can benefit from observing experienced teachers. Peer-to-peer coaching occurs when a teacher who is an expert in one area facilitates the understanding of other faculty members (Guinney, 2001). The form of coaching can be practical training or class observation. Teachers can also engage in their professional development through action research, which involves planning, acting, observing, and reflecting on classroom practice.

Factors impeding the integration of ict in teaching

The use of ICT to enhance learning faces numerous challenges, including financial limitations such as insufficient computer availability, a lack of computer proficiency among teachers, inadequate training in integrating ICT across different subjects, the absence of a well-structured curriculum for teaching computer

skills, and limited time for lesson preparation. The integration of ICT in schools and classrooms faces both external and internal barriers that can hinder its effective implementation. External challenges beyond individual teachers involve knowledge, skills, and training for effective ICT use (Nawzad, Rahim, & Said, 2018; Juggernath & Govender, 2020). Teachers, facing time constraints and resistance to change, often need more confidence due to limited training hours (Mathipa & Mukhari, 2014). Comprehensive ICT training boosts confidence and engagement, making learners more active participants (Mathipa & Mukhari, 2014). Leadership and support issues hinder ICT integration, with challenges in computer lab functionality and the absence of an ICT policy (Mathipa & Mukhari, 2014; Fu, 2013). The 'older generation cohort' may fear technology, emphasising the need for meaningful on-the-job training (Umugiraneza, Bansilal, & North, 2018). Teacher training is crucial for successful ICT integration, especially for the 'older generation' (Govender, 2018; Dube, Nhamo, & Magonde, 2018). Internal obstacles are ingrained in teachers' beliefs and practices, including attitudes toward and readiness for ICT (Chisango & Lesame, 2019). Some teachers harbour negative attitudes or feel uneasy about using ICT in front of learners (Buckenmeyer, 2010). Successful ICT integration depends on teachers' attitudes, adaptability, and competencies (Suryani, Soedarso, Prasetyowati, & Trisyanti, 2021). Dlamini & Mbatha's (2018) study revealed that teachers are uncomfortable using various ICT tools. Fu (2013) recommends ongoing professional development and workshops to address these challenges, transforming teaching into a learner-centred approach (Lu, Hou, & Huang, 2010). While ICT integration holds promise, more than the presence of resources is needed.

Blended learning approach

Unequal access to ICT infrastructure still exists as it is mostly limited to capital cities and major centres, leaving most people residing in rural or remote areas (Chisango & Marongwe, 2021). Thus, using blended learning strategies has been suggested as the most effective means of harnessing the potential of ICTs (Unwin, 2005). Blended learning is a flexible and effective educational approach that combines traditional face-to-face teaching with online learning components. In South Africa, like in many other countries, blended learning can be a valuable strategy to address various challenges and enhance the quality of education. Blended learning holds significant potential in addressing various educational challenges in South Africa. Firstly, it proves instrumental in overcoming issues related to access to education, particularly in remote or underserved areas, by providing online modules and resources, as highlighted in the UNESCO report on "Distance Education in South Africa" (UNESCO, 2009). The linguistic diversity of South Africa, with its 12 official languages, presents another hurdle, and blended learning can play a crucial role in offering language support through online resources and tutorials, making education more accessible for learners not proficient in the language of instruction, as discussed by Heugh, Siegrühn, and Plüddemann (2010).

Additionally, blended learning in teacher professional development aligns with the suggestions for new Teacher Education and Development frameworks, emphasising the importance of ongoing teacher development (Sancar, Atal & Deryakulu, 2021). Furthermore, blended learning facilitates personalised learning experiences through adaptive platforms, catering to individual student needs. Higher education contributes to the flexibility of learning options, supporting the goals outlined in the "White Paper for Post-School Education and Training" (DHET, 2013). The application of blended learning in technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programs aligns with the government's commitment to improving TVET in South Africa, as outlined in the "White Paper on Post-School Education and Training" (DHET, 2013). Moreover, incorporating online assessment tools in blended learning enhances the assessment and feedback process, as Cook and King (2019) explored in South African higher education. Lastly, blended learning facilitates resource sharing among educational institutions, benefiting under-resourced schools and universities and aligning with South African government policies and guidelines.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study followed an action research design. This methodology was chosen because I was interested in researching how teachers teach using ICT and sought to find practical solutions to their difficulties, potentially improving their teaching. This study adopts a participatory action research approach, focusing primarily on qualitative case study research. The primary aim of this research is to examine transformative actions undertaken to reshape the practices of practitioners (Mann & Walsh 2017, p. 222). These transformations encompass changes in their practices, their evolving understanding of these practices, and the contextual factors influencing their actions (Kemmis, 2009).

The study primarily centres on integrating the ISPD model within the action research cycle, encompassing activities such as professional discussions, curriculum development, peer observation, peer coaching and reflection. This cycle was repeated over four weeks.

Population and Sample

Intentionally, the research adopted a purposive sampling approach (Christiansen & Bertram, 2019) due to the school's well-established status and the presence of ample technological resources, including computers, tablets, smartboards, projectors, audio speakers and Wi-Fi. However, it should be noted that not all of these tools are fully integrated into the school's teaching and learning practices. The primary focus of this study was in a primary school (Grades R-7) located in the Gauteng district of Johannesburg South, South Africa, where English serves as the primary language of learning and teaching (LoLT). The study primarily centred around a Grade 6 Natural Sciences teacher with expertise and six years of teaching experience. The teacher responsible for Grade 6 and Grade 7 Natural Sciences was selected as the study's main participant and focus. Notably, despite her teaching proficiency, it's crucial to highlight that this teacher did not possess formal training in ICT and had never integrated ICT into her teaching methods. The involvement of learners in the study was not direct; instead, the teacher served as the sole participant. To select the study participant, I employed a non-probability sampling method, specifically relying on my professional network and my connections within the school. This approach was characterised by purposive sampling, wherein I reached out to teachers responsible for Natural Science teaching at the school where I am currently teaching.

Research Instruments

The instruments used were semi-structured interviews (professional discussion), with questions prepared and given to the teacher before the interview. The interview questions aimed to gather information on the educator's background, beliefs, attitude and pedagogy regarding ICT integration in teaching and learning. Classroom observation notes were used during the observation lesson to track teaching. Trainee journals were used in this study for their development and as a data source during discussion. Recently, journals have gained popularity in qualitative research because of their potential to provide in-depth, reflective information on sensitive issues. Guiding questions were provided to the participant: What are the main things you learned today, what went/did not go well, and what would you like to have in the next session? The choice of journaling at this study stage was pivotal to exploring the participants' experiences with the training. The training was conducted using Curriki Studio as the ICT tool, an exemplary technology platform designed to enhance the teaching of all subjects. Scott McNealy founded it in July 2020; Curriki Studio is an open-source technology platform created to facilitate the development of interactive lessons and immersive learning experiences.

Results and Discussion

The study revealed that one-on-one training by implementing the ISPD model sessions accommodated individual learning preferences, paces, and levels of ICT knowledge. This level of customised training promoted through the ISPD model empowered the teacher to progress quickly, ensuring that. The implantation of the ISPD model responded successfully to Fu's (2013) suggestion that schools should provide technology-related professional development activities to keep their teaching skills and knowledge up to date, offering technical assistance when necessary.

The hands-on training approach emerged as highly effective in this study, with the teacher favouring practical, experiential learning over traditional workshops. This supports Hennessy and Davies (2019) and Cothorn's (2020) finding that teachers learn best and effectively from one another. Eliminating a take a "top-down" approach to development. As literature by Dube, Nhamo and Magonde (2018) highlights, teacher training is important in determining whether teachers use ICT. The literature states that teachers' training programmes lack pedagogical training, preventing teachers from using ICTs in the classroom. This was evident in this study. During the reflection sessions, the teacher felt supported and guided through the training process. This was the cornerstone of a positive experience regarding ICT training for teachers. Teachers' responses to ICT training are significantly influenced by the level of support they receive, and this was evident during the study through the reflection discussion. Teacher training plays a pivotal role in determining whether teachers use ICT. Research findings revealed that teachers' training programmes lacked pedagogical training, preventing teachers from using ICTs in the classroom. A study conducted by Dube, Nhamo and Magonde (2018) further identified that although individual ICT skills for personal use may have been high, the challenge was transferring these skills to the classroom". Lack of access to continuous professional development activities was one of the issues raised by teachers in a study conducted by Dlamini and Mbatha (2018).

The teacher responded positively to the ISPD, expressing that the highlight was having access to an "expert" or knowledgeable trainer who could guide her through the complexities of integrating technology into her teaching. Unlike attending work for a few days and being expected to implement what she was taught without anyone to assist her when she faces challenges. She expressed that knowing that assistance is readily available boosted her confidence. When she encountered challenges or had questions, timely and helpful responses from the trainer were key. This prevented her from being frustrated and kept her engaged in learning. This supports

Hennessy and Davies (2019) and Cothorn's (2020) finding that teachers learn best and effectively from one another. Eliminating a take a “top-down” approach to development. As literature by Dube, Nhamo and Magonde (2018) highlights, teacher training is important in determining whether teachers use ICT.

Additionally, the teacher expressed how she appreciated and valued the personalised or tailored training experiences. She shared that having one-on-one training accommodated her and her learning/training preferences, making it easy for her to progress at her own pace and contributing to a more positive experience. Open discussions and sharing personal experiences created a positive learning environment during discussions and training. She actively engaged in dialogue about sensitive topics, fostering a deeper understanding of diversity issues and promoting a more inclusive workplace culture.

Constructive feedback and ongoing assessment of progress are essential. The teacher shared how positive feedback motivated her and gave her a sense of accomplishment. This recognition encouraged her to engage more in the training, benefiting her teaching methods. It also helped her understand her strengths and areas that required improvement. This way, she could measure her growth and continue training to improve her skills. Teachers participating in the study conducted by Dlamini and Mbatha (2018) raised the issue of appraisals. 40% say they never receive any feedback or appraisal on their performance. The need for appraisal also pointed at senior management teams not giving any type of feedback. The ISPD approach bridges these gaps. The immediate feedback on improvements allowed her to monitor her progress and work on improving her ICT skills. The teacher shared that collaborative learning with a peer who had also undergone ICT training benefited them. It allowed both teachers to identify gaps in their learning area and improve their teaching practice. The level of engagement during the training programme is a crucial factor. Engaging in training sessions is more effective in imparting new skills and knowledge.

Teachers assess whether the current programme is more relevant to their teaching needs than past workshops. A programme aligned with their subject areas and classroom challenges will likely receive positive feedback. The teacher shared that one of the gaps many workshops needed to address was to make their training relevant to their schools and classes. Instead, every teacher gets trained as though they face the same challenges. In that way, the workshops became irrelevant to their teaching, while customised training made it relevant for an individual school or teacher. The teacher responded more positively because she was actively involved in learning. The teacher completed real-world tasks. This active participation prepared her to apply her newly acquired skills in real leadership roles confidently. She learned how to use the software and understood its applications better, leading to a more profound knowledge acquisition.

The teacher responded positively when she received consistent support throughout the training process. Knowing that assistance was available at various stages of learning and implementation encouraged her to explore new technologies confidently. She was consistent and committed to the training. Supportive training programmes, such as the ISPD model, offered the participants clear guidance and opportunities for clarification. The teacher shared that she could grasp the training content better when she received thorough explanations and had access to resources. The emotional support was equally important. It created a safe and inclusive learning environment where the participant felt comfortable sharing her thoughts and experiences, fostering engagement. Time constraints and managing preparation time pose significant challenges for teachers when integrating ICT into their teaching, as observed and reflected on in this research study. More than traditional workshops may be needed in ICT teacher training to enhance ICT integration effectively. They often use a one-size-fits-all approach, not tailored to individual teachers or schools. This lack of differentiation can make some feel overwhelmed while others disengage. Time constraints limit in-depth exploration, leaving teachers with surface-level knowledge. Follow-up support like ISPD is necessary for workshop knowledge to be sustainable, undermining professional development (Loucks-Horsley & Stiles, 2006). Initially, the teacher struggled to balance her classes, administrative tasks and ICT training sessions. However, she recognised the need for adaptation to accommodate her professional growth. This led to her willingness to allocate free periods and personal time at home for skill improvement. The teacher and trainer collaboratively developed a timetable with administrative sessions to ensure a balanced workload. Allocating specific time for tasks at work and home proved beneficial. She expressed that this taught her the importance of planning in teaching and learning. She realised that she did have time and could make time to improve her teaching.

Conclusion

ISPD for teachers encompasses a range of activities and experiences that are aimed at helping teachers enhance their knowledge, skills, and effectiveness in any field in the classroom. The aim is to provide continuous training that empowers teachers to stay abreast of educational trends, technologies and methodologies (Guskey, 2002). The ISPD model is precious for effectively integrating ICT in teaching and learning. The purpose was for

teachers to gain the skills and confidence needed to integrate technology in the classroom to support learning and engagement. The teacher's positive experience with ICT training and integration was a testament to the significance of support, guidance and customisation in professional development. The main finding is that the ISPD model has a more significant and positive influence on teachers' ICT beliefs, motivation and integration. This suggests that the ISPD approach effectively fostered positive changes in teachers' perspectives, enthusiasm and practical use of ICT within their teaching practice.

Recommendations

In light of the above findings, the study recommends the following: To gain a more comprehensive and prolonged perspective on the effectiveness of ICT training through ISPD, a more extended study conducted over an entire school term or academic year would be valuable. Long-term studies provide a greater depth of insight into the ISPD programme. Long-term studies are well-suited for assessing the lasting impact of interventions, programmes or policies over an extended duration (Gelman & Hill, 2006). Researchers should consider employing representative sampling methods to gain valuable insights, ensuring that the sample size is adequate for drawing meaningful conclusions and accounting for differences within distinct grade levels and subjects. Investigating how the ISPD model would work with different teachers from different phases, such as in the foundation phase where the teacher must teach all the subjects (English, Afrikaans, Mathematics and Life Skills). Comparative analyses should be conducted to examine whether the ISPD model's effectiveness differs when implemented with teachers from various grade levels. This comparative approach, including higher and lower grades, could reveal important information about the programme's impact on different educational stages.

Evaluating the impact of ICT training on student learning outcomes is a crucial component of assessing the effectiveness of ICT training and integration for teaching and learning. A comprehensive evaluation could investigate whether learners taught by teachers who received ISPD training achieve better results in subjects like science or others than those taught by teachers who did not. This analysis would provide a deeper understanding of the programme's effectiveness and areas for improvement. Furthermore, a longitudinal study could be conducted to explore whether learners of teachers who received ICT training through ISPD demonstrate enhanced performance in subsequent grades. Although the national e-education policy exists, it often remains invisible within the school context when no value is attached to its use (Cheng, Lu, Xie, & Vongkulluksn, 2020).

Furthermore, the lack of policy support and school district presence was a significant concern (Inan & Lowther, 2010; Tondeur, van Keer, van Braak, & Valcke, 2008). These findings emphasise the pressing need for a more comprehensive understanding of ICT policy and its practical implementation, especially within South African schools. To enhance the effective use of ICT in education, greater efforts should be directed toward bridging the gap between policy intent and classroom practice. Therefore, the government should focus on developing ICT policies at the school level and ensuring their successful implementation. Moreover, future research could explore strategies for bridging this policy-practice gap (Tondeur, van Keer, van Braak, & Valcke, 2008).

In conclusion, the study underscores the effectiveness of the ISPD model in professional development, fostering positive attitudes and comprehensive support systems in facilitating effective ICT integration in education. It advocates for a collaborative effort involving teachers, school management teams and policymakers to provide the necessary training, resources and policy support. Ultimately, the successful integration of ICT is essential for learners' holistic teaching and prospects, not only in South Africa but in education contexts worldwide. This model introduced an innovative and cost-effective approach to providing personalised, effective training to enhance teaching and learning. It streamlined ongoing training, offering convenient access for both trainers and trainees. This approach allowed for customised, individualised and ICT-specific teacher training, departing from the one-size-fits-all approach.

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